

MORAL CRITERIA OF PATRIOTIC VIRTUE

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the phenomenon of youth patriotism in the process of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan, the priority tasks of education of patriotism in young people in the process of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan are studied. Also, the need to study the processes of spiritual growth of New Uzbekistan and the factors that develop it is analyzed.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, scientific-methodological basis, socio-philosophical, phenomenon, spiritual growth, patriotism, modernity, historical-philosophical basis, objectivity, historicity, systematicity, analysis, synthesis, induction-deduction.

INTRODUCTION. In the current era, patriotism is required to become a characteristic characteristic of young people who deeply respect the history and fate of the motherland, people, and are able to show examples of selflessness in the interests of the Motherland. Because, only when love for the motherland and trust in its future are formed on the basis of a single goal aimed at the interests of the nation, patriotism becomes a virtue of all people who connect their fate with the fate of the homeland and the nation. Therefore, the virtue of patriotism requires everyone to take responsibility for their work, preserve and protect the Motherland, strive to maintain peace, stability and tranquility in the country, and put the interests of the Motherland and the nation first in international relations.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The processes of spiritual growth in Uzbekistan are promoted on the basis of the principle of "From national revival to national growth", conceptual ideas in the works, speeches, articles and selective meetings of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as well as the philosophical heritage of the East and the West. serves as a scientific-methodological basis for this research.

A number of studies have been carried out that include the problems related to clarifying the importance of the processes of spiritual growth in the new stage of development of Uzbekistan. S. Shermuhammedov, A. Saidov, B. Toraev, J. Yakhshilikov, N. Joraev, Q. Nazarov, S. Otamurodov, S. Karimov, A. Kholbekov, R. Jumaev, B. Karimov, T. Our scientists, such as Joraev, I. Ergashev, S. Joraev, M. Kyrgyzboev, A. Erkaev, M. Bekmurodov, V. Kochkarov, M. Jakbarov, A. Muminov, have conducted various researches on the development of the social sphere in society. carried out. Scientists such as R. Ubaidullaeva, Kh. Abdusattorova have conducted research on the importance of the innovative factor in the new era of social development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In our opinion, it is necessary to analyze the moral values of everyday activities in order to visualize patriotism more clearly. Among such virtues are the following patriotism, duty, responsibility, honor, pride, humanity, kindness, brotherhood, faith, nobility, determination, dedication, conscientiousness, performance, responsibility, independence, obedience, such positive aspects as enthusiasm, altruism, integrity,

truthfulness, professionalism, justice, awareness, hard work, sincerity and so on. Also, bravery, bravery, fearlessness, heroism, bravery, strength, ambition, bravery, endurance, bravery and other positive aspects are among the martial virtues that show loyalty to the motherland. It should be noted that patriotism is connected to the ancient history and spiritual sources of our national heritage. Because the formation of moral qualities such as pride, honor, honor, trust and loyalty in young people becomes a reality based on the conditions of patriotism.

In addition, glorifying the patriotism of our grandfathers such as Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Najmuddin Kubro, Temur Malik, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur as a moral ideal, and a deeper analysis of the sources reflecting their moral views and life activities related to the virtue of patriotism will instill patriotism in young people. serves to further increase.

In the moral values of the Uzbek people, patriotism is valued as a characteristic characteristic of people who are able to show examples of selflessness in the defense of the country, looking at the country's history and destiny with deep respect. This feeling is formed on the basis of moral concepts such as "love", "trust", "loyalty" and is a philosophical category that has not lost its status over the years because it has taken a deep place in the hearts of people. Patriotism is glorified in all sources related to the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, as it embodies moral qualities such as unification, orientation, cohesion, and mobilization. Islam, which is considered our highest spiritual value, is no exception.

It is known that it makes it possible to advance considerations on the construction of a model of the spiritual and moral value system that forms patriotism. In particular, the model of the spiritual and moral value system of patriotism, which is studied as a systematized complex at a certain level, includes several components, including the following:

- 1) the formation of patriotism is a process that includes many elements that form its structural integrity;
- 2) the formation of patriotism is somewhat complicated, regulated and reduced to a unique system;
- 3) patriotism has certain pagan levels, and these levels are subordinate to each other;
- 4) patriotism is always influenced by internal and external forces, and its development requires maintaining stability;
- 5) the formation of patriotism is flexible in terms of adapting to changing conditions, enriches its content based on the requirements of the time;
- 6) the formation of patriotism has a character that forms the main system;
- 7) patriotism has the ability to develop itself and enriches its spirituality;
- 8) patriotism has the characteristic of development based on historical consistency;
- 9) the formation of patriotism requires the implementation of many functional tasks and requires the satisfaction of a number of basic requirements.

The moral criteria of patriotism include self-sacrifice, responsibility, heroism, endurance, loyalty, piety and pride. As a result of scientific analysis, we consider it appropriate to interpret the content of these criteria as follows:

1. Devotion. Self-sacrifice is an important moral criterion of the virtue of patriotism. Self-sacrifice requires a person to have a big heart, enthusiasm, and most importantly, strong faith in oneself and one's own strength. The patriotism of young people requires self-sacrifice, tireless mobilization of oneself towards great goals, turning this quality into a constant, daily

activity criterion.

2. Duty. This concept is important because of its indirect nature of patriotism. Because the duty of patriotism is a responsible duty of a person towards the society and the state. Lack of sense of duty, irresponsibility - a sign of indifference and indifference to the interests of the country, the people, and the problems of the future. Our ancient ancestors developed a whole set of moral requirements for a perfect person to understand his duties and responsibilities.

3. Responsibility. Responsibility is a moral factor aimed at realizing duty and acting based on it. Responsibility means personal responsibility for the fulfillment of tasks of social and moral importance, as well as for following the moral principles underlying the behavior.

4. Heroism. Inosn's display of physical and spiritual courage directly demonstrates his heroism. Heroism is a sign of courage. Because to be enthusiastic in everyday life, to show selflessness every day, to never give up mentally, to raise this quality to the level of a rule of life, frankly, not everyone can do it. This requires a great heart and strong will from a person.

5. Endurance. It is not only to endure any difficulties, but also to overcome them for the benefit of the Motherland.

6. Loyalty. This quality is manifested through loyalty to the Motherland, duty, and valuing solidarity, solidarity, and friendship. Loyalty, especially a person's loyalty to the Motherland, honesty, conscientiousness, consistency, living with concern for the country, ultimately forms views and knowledge related to the place in the development of society. It is determined by their moral maturity in the spirit of loyalty to the country and their contribution to the material and spiritual development of society.

7. Pride. This quality becomes a reality through the feeling of pride in the success, honor, achievements and values of the people and the nation. This feeling is manifested in the following forms: pride in the achievements and prestige of the nation, not looking indifferently at its problems; to be passionate about one's country and nation; to preserve the material and spiritual heritage of one's nation; respect, enrich and improve people's customs, traditions, values; to show love for one's nation in practical activities.

8. Oriyat. This is to refrain from actions, things, words, actions that are inappropriate or unacceptable to oneself, to be embarrassed, to be ashamed; to protect one's self-respect, not to lose one's reputation.

In addition, the virtue of patriotism is formed on the basis of virtues such as courage, involvement, sympathy for state policy. In turn, each of them combines a number of features in its structure. Including:

A). Courage. To feel the invincible strength and power in one's body, to strive to have the name of brave, to form views and knowledge related to raising qualities such as bravery and honesty, bravery to the level of human duty. To consider justice above all else is to be a patriotic and courageous person who feels responsibility for history and the future.

B). Affection. To fundamentally change the attitude to the fate of the homeland, to the events happening around, to strengthen high moral qualities, democratic values, to be involved in large-scale reforms, to form a sense of confidence in the future of our country. It is necessary to consciously look at the reality of today's rapidly changing life, to live with independent thinking and a sense of belonging to all changes in our country.

V). Sympathy for public policy. To build a powerful state is to feel the civic duty, to be an active participant in the implementation of state policy. The priority goal of the state policy

implemented in our country is to realize such dreams and hopes of our people, to create decent living conditions for our people in all respects.

At the same time, a person's moral behavior and moral attitude to reality depend on his inner feelings and emotional experiences. These experiences are usually called virtues, depending on the good deeds of the person, and vices, depending on the bad deeds. Virtues show that a person is worthy of praise as a social essence, while vices prevent a person from being great. In the formation, strengthening and realization of patriotic feelings, there is a sharp struggle between virtue and vice. This is an eternal struggle, which essentially requires a dialectical conflict.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it follows that the concepts of patriotism, selflessness, loyalty, love of the country have different conceptual aspects based on their moral foundations, different aspects and dialectical connection. Therefore, in the formation of patriotism in young people, it is necessary to proceed from their views, national and ethnic qualities, and approach them based on this.

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